

Topic	Regex
operator_overloads	"\boperator\s*([\s(]+)\s*\([\^\)]*\)\s*\{"
virtual_function	"\bvirtual\s+[\^;]+([\^\)]*\)\s*(?:const)?\s*\{"
Friend function	"\bfriend\s+[\^;]+([\^\)]*\)\s*\{"
try_catch	"\btry\s*\{" "\bcatch\s*\([\^\)]*\)\s*\{"
Inline	"\binline\s+[\^;]+([\^\)]*\)\s*\{"
templates	"\btemplate\s*<[\^>]+\>\s*\([\^\)]*\)\s*\{"
classes	"\bclass\s+\w+\s*\{"
inheritance	"class\s+\w+\s*:\s*\w+\s*\{"

Highlight threshold: 1.2

Topic	window_size
operator overload	20
virtual function	40
friend	40
Inheritance	60
inline	10
templates	40
Classes	20
Try_Catch	60